

USING EFFECTIVE CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT OF DIFFERENT COUNTRIES IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

Our rapidly evolving educational system is aiming to successfully teach many foreign languages, mainly English. Based on the experience of the most educated countries, this article offers a few precise and highly effective methods for classroom management in English instruction.

Key words: foreign countries, setting rules, ESL, friendly environment, classroom management.

INTRODUCTION

Some educational phrases are so unclear that it's difficult to figure out what they really mean and how teachers can use them in the classroom. Classroom management is one of the most perplexing problems in education. Every teacher should be able to facilitate it in order to maintain a productive classroom environment. The term, on the other hand, can mean a variety of things and be used to learning settings in a variety of ways.

Classroom management at its most basic level, is any approach used by teachers to facilitate education and ensure that students learn most effectively in a calm classroom setting. Having a systematic system in place that establishes standards for student behavior in the classroom can aid in the most effective management of the classroom environment, ensuring that students are held accountable for their actions and behaviors.

Depending on the subject, age group, or educational instruments employed, classroom management might vary. For example, management strategies for an art

class will be very different from those for a computing class. Students are responsible for cleaning and properly caring for supplies used in an art lesson. The noise level requirements in that class will differ from those in a computer class, where pupils are expected to concentrate on their gadgets and the lesson at hand. Whether you are an art teacher or a computer teacher (or anywhere in between), having a plan for classroom management is critical. The goal for all teachers is to have an organized, productive, and safe environment for students in their classrooms.

It's very vital at the start of a semester to have a clear description and expectation of your classroom management system. This allows you to set such expectations for students on the first day of class so that when it comes time to praise or criticize behaviors later in the semester, students are aware of the standards they met or did not fulfill.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ideal Classroom Management in Japan

In compliance with Kawamura (2010), the characteristics of Anglo-American classroom communities differ from those of Japanese classroom communities. He uses the terms "society" and "community" to explain the distinction. A society is a group of people who come together to achieve a common goal, and a community is formed through links such as blood ties, territorial ties, and shared beliefs. Anglo-American classroom communities have significant traits of society as a learning group with the goal of achieving academic success, as well as clearly defined norms and behaviors for participation in the groups. Japanese classroom communities, on the other hand, are built on the foundation of community, with the goal of facilitating children's psychosocial development while also serving as a learning group. As a result, Japanese teachers believe that the ideal class includes elements of both society and community, such as rules for human relations, group activities, and group life (hereafter referred to as the rules), as well as open communication and honest emotional exchange (hereafter referred to as the relations) (Kawamura, 2007; Kawamura, 2010). According to the degree of the establishment of rules and relations, Kawamura (2007, pp. 19-23) divided Japanese classes into five categories.

Finland classroom management

Most American teachers cannot imagine taking a 15-minute break every 45 minutes of classroom instruction like the Finnish do. However, these short breaks would provide students with time to get refreshed before the next lesson begins and help teachers to increase their productivity during the class.

According to D. Timothy, many American teachers would likely face opposition from parents and administrators if they introduced a Finnish-style schedule, but he believes it is still viable to execute this research-backed technique while maintaining academic standards.

In "Teach Like Finland," I recommend that students have "option time" multiple times a day, where they have roughly 10 minutes to disconnect from the typical focused coursework. On these days, students can pick from a variety of engaging classroom activities, such as playing a fun math puzzler on their own or reading an interesting book at their independent reading level. Although it isn't exactly free play, choosing time would allow pupils to relax for a few moments before the next lecture begins. [Timothy D:2017,210-213p]

Classroom management in Korea

Always engage and inspire your students

In the classroom, students' motivation is like a rollercoaster. They will be perfectly focused one minute and then put their heads on their desks, drooling on their books, or disrupting others because they have lost interest the next. Keeping your pupils engaged will keep them motivated to study and behave in the ways you want them to, reducing the need for disciplinary measures. So, each teacher besides making their lesson plans, being mindful of the educational quality and curriculum goals, but they also need to remember that teacher's role there is to make learning English gripping!

Korean learners prefer learning English by playing games and other interactive learning activities, so it becomes natural for them.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Consider how you can teach your students English to create interest

1) Knowing your pupils' names is the most important factor in classroom management. If you can't recall who they are, check their clothes or desks for name tags. When you're describing an exercise or in the middle of a discussion and notice a student who isn't paying attention, address them by their name right away. You either ask questions or get them to conduct an activity relating to the present topic to pull them back into the conversation. You might, for example, post writing assignments on the board that you've explained with the help of other students. This leads to group conversations, ensuring that all kids in the classroom are aware of what is going on. There are two major advantages to addressing a student by their first name. To begin with, the student feels significant since you know their name instead of pointing at them and shouting, "Hey, you!" Second, knowing that the teacher is paying attention

enough to remember their name reassures them that the teacher is always aware of what they are doing. [*Journal Kourvia Consulting : 2015. 46-49-pages*]

Do not mistake your students' lack of English for their lack of intelligence

Even if they are incorrect, always congratulate and support your pupils' attempts to answer. However, the erroneous English should not be overlooked. Praise and affirm their responses, and then demonstrate to the pupils what needs to be improved. This is where the education begins. Make your kids follow your lead and repeat the correct pattern. You're not telling them they're wrong this way; instead, you're encouraging them to speak up and making them proud of what they've accomplished.

These tactics, in our opinion, should be implemented in our country, particularly in secondary schools, where there is a lack of interest in learning new things. Furthermore, if teachers are simply severe and discriminate for students' bad behavior and low grades, teenagers may disrespect their teachers and lose their interest to learning.

Prove the Learning

Despite the fact that Finland's schools use limited standardized testing, children are still tested. They feel that having pupils "show their understanding by defending their answers" encourages them to think critically and imaginatively. Create tasks that require students to provide reasons for why they would vote for a particular political candidate, or to explain how the media fights for viewers. This demonstrates true comprehension.

Do not get discouraged!

The key to classroom management while teaching English to young learners is to be willing to try different ways in order to see if they work, such as establishing and enforcing clear rules with obvious consequences and modeling good behavior. If something goes wrong, don't get discouraged. "You tried and you learned!" is a better way of looking at "falling short."

Pre-teaching to your classroom expectations is one of the secrets to good classroom management presented in the program. Not every student, in every classroom, in every school, for example, understands how to follow orders. You may need to explain to your students what "following directions" means in your classroom, rather than presuming that every student can do so, on their own.

Consider this:

What should we do if a student is unable to read?

We teach.

What do we do if a student does not know how to swim?

We teach.

What should we do if a learner is unable to multiply?

We teach.

So, what do you do if a student does not know how to “get ready for math”?

You teach.

CONCLUSION

Finally, classroom management is beneficial to the achievement of the students. What pupils learn and how much they learn will be jeopardized if good classroom management is not in place. Simply articulating rules clearly and going through processes on a daily basis can help to reduce disruptions and confusion. Establishing an incentive structure that rewards both effort and achievement encourages students to obey rules and fosters self-regulation, helping them to make better decisions and be more productive. Teachers should encourage their kids to appreciate the topic, respect other cultures, and travel around the world with their bright-eyed children because learning a second language is a difficult undertaking.

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